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EDDU Protocols

High Content Imaging, Analysis and Data Management

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The purpose of this document is to outline the workflow from data generation to data storage and analysis using the ThermoFisher Scientific CellInsight CX7 High Content Screening (HCS) Platform in fluorescence-based cellular assays. It provides guidelines on image acquisition, image analysis and data management.

1.2 High Content System overview

The CellInsight CX7 platform consists of a fully automated light microscope, image acquisition and analysis software and a storage server. The light microscope provides 7 fluorescence channels both in widefield and (spinning disk) confocal mode as well as several brightfield color options. The motorized stage in combination with the autofocus and the freely configurable microplate database enables to scan microplates from 6 well to 1536 well format, slides and costume plates. Objective choices range from x4 to x40 air objectives. Control over all configurations is provided by the image acquisition software. Images can be directly analyzed in the software as they are acquired or post-acquisition. For analysis, a variety of protocol templates are provided. Images, metadata and analysis results are stored on a separate server in a relational (SQL) database and can be exported for further analysis and documentation in several formats. More information about the system can be found on the [Thermofisher CX7 website](#) .

1.3 Protocol overview

Careful development of the assay of interest and adaption to the requirements of automated imaging and analysis is essential for a successful HCS experiment. While assay development is beyond the scope of this protocol, some important aspects to consider are summarized in **section 1.4**. This protocol describes the necessary steps to acquire and analyze images using the HCS Studio Scan software (**Figure 1**). In almost all cases, experiments are based on multiplexed fluorescence staining of cells, cell aggregates and/ or subcellular structures. The quality of the images is critically important to accurately identify objects of interest in images and the necessary steps to ensure good quality are described. The choice of the analysis template to identify objects and obtain their properties depends on the research question and can range from simple measurements of morphological cell features (e.g. nuclear size, shape and/or intensity) to complex shapes (e.g. neurite outgrowth) and dynamic processes (e.g. intracellular trafficking and cell migration). This protocol explains the general workflow of this step-by-step process and highlights the critical parameters to be optimized in any of the provided analysis sequences. Images and image analysis data is stored on the Studio server. The protocol describes access to the server, image and numerical data visualization and data retrieval via the HCS Studio View software.

Figure 1. HCS workflow: 1) CX7, Image acquisition and image (primary) analysis. 2) Image and primary data storage on Studio server. 3) Data retrieval and data (secondary) analysis.

1.4 Technical and safety considerations

This protocol should be used as a guideline. It does not replace training on the CX7 HCS instrument by qualified personnel. In addition, a working knowledge of light microscopy, particularly fluorescence microscopy, is considered essential. At the EDDU, after training is deemed sufficient, new users will be assigned an account to log on to the CX7 HCS instrument as well as an account for an online booking system that allows to manage instrument availability by the multiple users of the platform.

Before starting any new experiment, the following aspects should be taken into consideration during assay development:

- **Plate format:** Any microplate format that respects the ANSI/SLAS microplate standards (see [SLAS industry standards website](#)) can be used. The choice depends, for example, on the number and size of wells and the optical quality of the material required for the assay. Note that the plate dimensions must be entered into the CX7 labware database if they are not already listed.
- **Cells:** In many experiments, the choice of cell type is dictated by the research question. In general, flat, strongly attached, and well spread cells are ideal for HCS applications (consider coating the wells to increase adherence and spreading). Cell density should be titrated to find an optimal compromise between identification of cells and sufficiently high cell number per image field. In general, for flat, adherent single cells ~80% confluence is considered ideal, for cells growing in aggregates other criteria (e.g. aggregate size) might be more useful.
- **Objectives:** Available objectives range from x4 to x40 magnification, some are available with different numerical apertures. The actual objective choice depends on the experimental goal of the assay and can range from low magnification overviews e.g. of cell aggregates to high magnification images to interrogate subcellular structures.
- **Positive/ negative controls:** Controls are an essential part of any assay/ experiment. For HCS-type assays in particular, controls are needed to determine thresholds for object detection, evaluation of effects on assay parameters and determination of assay quality (e.g. Z').
- **Object identification (counterstain):** In most experimental approaches, all objects of interest (e.g. cells/ cell aggregates) have to be identified; usually by a counterstain that is independent of the experimental manipulations (e.g. nuclear stains like Hoechst33342, or cellular stains like WGA or Cell Mask). The choice of the counterstain depends on the experimental question and the fluorescence wavelength required.
- **Data management:** During the planning of an experiment, a plate map of the microplate should be generated from a template (e.g. Excel sheet) to identify the content, treatment, volumes, etc. in each well.
- **Data safety:** Images and image analysis data generated during a scan are automatically stored on the STUDIO server in a SQL database. By factory default the database is backed-up continuously on the server. Additional off-site back-ups should be considered. In addition, a strategy to keep the relationship between the original scan data and data exported from the server, results from secondary analysis, and other experimental data (e.g. plate maps)

should be implemented. For more information on the EDDU back-up organisation system, see **Appendix 3.1**.

1.5 Equipment

Item	Supplier	Catalogue #
CellInsight CX7	ThermoFisher Scientific	CX7, SN: L0716-190A-008

1.6 Software

Item	Supplier	version
HCS Studio Scan	ThermoFisher Scientific	6.6.1 Build 8468
HCS Studio View	ThermoFisher Scientific	6.6.1 Build 8468
STORE database	ThermoFisher Scientific	1.6
Excel 2016	Microsoft	16.0.4266.1001
Python 2.7	Python.org	v.2.7.15

3. Click **Create (Figure 2B)** to open the chosen template. This will open the **Configure Acquisition** tab.
4. Click on insert plate Symbol (**Figure 3A**) to move the microplate tray out of the instrument. Put the microplate with well A1 pointing towards you. Click on the same button to move tray back into the instrument.
5. Set the following conditions for image acquisition (**Figure 3: Configure Acquisition Tab.**):
 - **Objective:** 4x, 10x, 20x, or 40x magnification
 - **Camera Acquisition Mode:** default is 1104x1104 (2x2 binning)
 - **Autofocus setup:** default is software autofocus, each field; Standard
 - Number of **Channels** (1-6) and appropriate filter sets for each channel and/or brightfield settings.
 - **Plate form factor:** choose the relevant microplate from the drop-down menu (**Figure 3C**).

2.1.2 Acquisition optimization and collection of test images:

1. Select a well where the highest fluorescence intensity values are expected.
 2. Acquire image in channel 1 (primary channel) using **Software Autofocus (Figure 3D)**. Verify in pixel intensity histogram (**Contrast Controls, Modify Contrast Settings**) that signal is well within dynamic range of the camera (**Figure 3E, Figure 4**).
 3. If the pixel intensity histogram is out of range, increase or lower **Exposure Time (Figure 3F)** accordingly and collect image again using **Acquire Image**.
 4. Collect images in all other channels (**Acquire Image** or **Acquire Image Set**) ensuring a good dynamic range is achieved with appropriate exposure times.
- If the images in any of secondary channels are out of focus, use the **Z-Offset** to adjust the focus in that channel (**Figure 3G**).

Figure 3: Configure Acquisition Tab. A) Insert plate button. B) Image acquisition parameters. C) Plate type drop-down menu. D) Manual focus and image acquisition. E) Pixel intensity histogram. F) Exposure time entry field. G) Z-offset adjustment.

Figure 4: Pixel Intensity histogram of the same field taken with three different exposure times. 1) Too low exposure time results in loss of dynamic range and compressed signal values. 2) Good exposure time with wide coverage of dynamic range. 3) Too high exposure time results in clipping (saturation) of high intensity pixels.

5. Collect image sets from at least three more wells, always using **Software autofocus** in channel 1 first, and then **Acquire Image Set** for all channels. These will be used to set up the analysis template. The choice of image sets depends on the experiment and analysis templates.

- Ideally, selected wells should cover different areas of the plate.

- If the intensity or morphology of the primary objects changes between wells due to different experimental conditions, image sets should be taken from each of those conditions (or at least the most diverse) to ensure that objects can be properly identified under all conditions.
- If thresholds are used to distinguish between cells with and without a given signal, negative controls (no stain in that channel) serve to set the threshold above background.
- For each condition 3-4 image sets are usually enough for analysis set up. However, if variability is high in any condition, more sets might be necessary to balance analysis conditions.

2.1.3 Setting of analysis parameters:

6. Select the **Configure Assay Parameters** tab. Under **Layout (Figure 5A)**, select **Configure groups** to open the plate map with the already acquired image sets. Double-click on fields from a selected well to load image sets into the assay template. Up to 10 image sets can be assigned into two groups. To view the images from 2 groups in parallel (e.g. positive and negative controls) set the **Groups to Display** in **Layout**.

Figure 5: Configure Assay Parameters Tab. A) Interface layout. B) Step by step assay protocol task list. C) Image window task bar. D) Image Settings (per channel).

7. Optimize the parameter settings for image analysis by going through the **Protocol Optimization Task List (Figure 5B)** from top to bottom.
- While the parameters are based on the protocol chosen, the general workflow is similar for most assays (**Table 1**). For a detailed description of each protocol, please refer to the help menu in the software (**BioApplicationHelp**).

- During the optimization, toggle between image sets (wells and fields) to verify settings (**Figure 5C**).
- To visualize the parameter values measured in an image, select **Data** and/ or **Statistics** in **Layout** (**Figure 5A**).
- To modify the displayed image (in each channel), use the **Image Settings** block (**Figure 5D**).

Table 1 Protocol Optimization Steps

	Step	Description	Features	Channel
1	Preprocess Image	Background removal	Background removal yes/no and stringency	All channels
2	Identify Primary Objects	Find objects (e.g. nuclei, cells), generates mask	Threshold modification, object separation	Channel 1
3	Validate Primary Objects	Filter objects by morphological and intensity-based features	-Border objects -Object Area/Shape -Object Total/Average/Variance Intensity	Channel 1
4	Select Primary Objects	Filter objects in channels (ROI-based)	-Object Total/ Average Intensity	Channel 2-6
5	Identify Targets/ Spots Channel x	Secondary objects identification (e.g. neurites, vesicles)	Protocol dependent, e.g. intensity threshold, spot detection, neurite detection/identification	Channel 2-6
6	Reference Levels	Population identification (High and Low responders)	Set Low/ High thresholds for all features calculated in section 1-5	All channels

2.1.4 Scan set-up

8. In the **Population Characterization** tab, set **Scan Limits** to define the number of fields scanned per well (**Figure 6A**). Additional **Stopping criteria** can be defined to avoid scanning empty or sparse wells.
9. Optionally, define sub-populations based on the extracted protocol features using Boolean operators (**Event Subpopulations, Figure 6B**). The output is given as the percentage of objects fulfilling the Boolean criteria per well.

Figure 6: Population Characterization Tab. A) Scan limits, maximal fields per well (arrow). B) Event Subpopulations to combine selection criteria through Boolean operators.

10. Under the **Select Features to Store** tab, define the features and statistics to be written to the database.

- From the full list of extracted features, values can be selected that will be stored with the scan on a per cell and on a per well basis (**Figure 7A**). This can include values for each individual object (per cell data) and average values for each well (mean, SD, SE, CV, %High and %Low) for each channel. Features are transferred from the “available” list to the “selected” list, using the arrows in between (**Figure 7B**). In some assay protocols per field values can also be chosen.
- Since per well data is not very storage demanding, it is recommended to keep all per well data. Per cell data should be chosen according to the experimental question.

- The **Enable Kinetics** button under this tab can be used to set up a time course for image acquisition in live experiments (**Figure 7C**). More information on kinetics can be found in the Help menu.

Figure 7: Select Features To Store Tab. A) Well/ Field/ Cell tabs for feature selection. B) Select/ deselect features in each tab. C) Enable and configure time course image acquisition.

- In the **Scan plate** tab, select the wells to be scanned by clicking on the plate icon under **Scan Settings (Figure 8A)**. The order in which the fields are scanned can also be modified from this window (default is spiraling outward from the center).
 - Under **Plate Name** and **Plate ID (Figure 8B)** enter the plate name (e.g. *date (yyyymmdd)-experiment*).
- Each plate scan will also be assigned a machine-generated **Unique Plate Description**, following the nomenclature: *233-drucker-pc1(ComputerName)_YYMMDDHH (date and hour) xxxx (running number)*.
- Save the protocol under **File → Save as** and start the scan by clicking the arrow under **Scan Controls (Figure 8C)**.
- An estimate of the total scanning time will be posted as soon as the first well is completed and readjusted as the scan progresses.
 - Extracted features of already scanned wells can be visualized in the **Plate/ Data** tabs using the **Well Feature** drop down menu (**Figure 8D**).
 - The Scan can be paused or stopped at any time under **Scan Controls**.

Figure 8: Scan Plate Tab. A) Scan settings, well selection. B) Plate name and ID (user defined). C) Start/pause/ stop scan field. D) Well feature selection for real time per well results. E) Direct link to final scan images and results in Studio View.

2.2 Retrieval of data and data processing

14. To access the data once the scan is finished, use **Launch View** on the **Scan** tab to open Studio View (**Figure 8E**). Alternatively, open **View** from the **HCS Studio** navigator, click on **Change Filters** (**Figure 9A**) and search the database (e.g. Plate ID or date of scan, **Figure 9B**). In the list of search results (**Figure 9C**), double click on the scan of choice and select all well features to be loaded.

Figure 9: View database search window. A) Access to search parameters. B) Search parameter list. C) List of search results (per plate).

15. Choose any feature of interest (**Figure 10A**) to visualize as a graphical (**Figure 10B**) or numerical representation (**Figure 10C**).
16. Right-click on the graph or plate map to access the following (**Figure 10D**):
- Image Browser (**Browse Images in iView**) to view and configure acquired images, tiles, overlays and masks, and to export sample images.
 - Single cell data (**Cell Details**) displays per feature basis data, images, and overlays for each cell in a well, including a histogram of the feature for all cells.
 - Export single cell data per well (**Export to Spotfire, csv or txt**)

Figure 10: View, plate data. A) Per plate list of extracted features. B) Graphical representation of one selected feature (per well). C) Numerical representation of selected feature (per well as plate map). D) Image and data handling commands (right click to access).

17. Export data: There are 2 options:

- Choose feature to export and go to **Spreadsheet, Export Current Spreadsheet, to File**. This will export the feature chosen as an .xls file in plate map format. Every feature has to be exported separately.
- Choose **Data/ Image Export Tool**. This application is accessed through the plate list window in **View (Figure 9)** by right-click on the scan to be exported. It allows to combine several features and export them in one list.

3 Appendix

3.1 Data back-up for EDDU

At the EDDU, each user in the lab owns a designated folder in the lab's online server space (ownCloud, <https://box.bic.mni.mcgill.ca>). The space is maintained on the computer grid of the MNI McConnell Brain Imaging Center with daily incremental backups. In addition, bi-weekly full backups are stored for at least one month. Folders containing experimental data are stored in this space, either by frequently uploading the data or by linking a local folder to ownCloud for continuous synchronisation (recommended). The HCS Studio server is also housed in the Brain Imaging Center. This server is mirrored continuously with copies being generated daily and kept for one week off-site.